

Reviewer Acknowledgements

Review of European Studies wishes to acknowledge the following individuals for their assistance with peer review of manuscripts for this issue. Their help and contributions in maintaining the quality of the journal is greatly appreciated.

Many authors, regardless of whether *Review of European Studies* publishes their work, appreciate the helpful feedback provided by the reviewers.

Reviewers for Volume 13, Number 1

Ali S.M. Al-Issa, Sultan Qaboos University, Oman

Aziollah Arbabisarjou, Zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Iran

Ezgi Pelin Yildiz, Kafkas University, Turkey

Federico De Andreis, University Giustino Fortunato, Italy

Florin Ionita, The Bucharest Academy of Economic Studies, Romania

Gabriela Gruber, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania

Gülce Başer, Boğaziçi University, Turkey

Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, 'Timotheus' Brethren Theological Institute of Bucharest, Romania

Ismail Affero, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia

Ludmila Ivancheva, Institute of Philosophy and Sociology at Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria

Meenal Tula, University of Hyderabad, India

Natalija Vrecer, independent researcher, Slovenia

Nunzia Di Cristo Bertali, Liverpool John Moores University, United Kingdom

Patrick van Esch, Moravian College, Australia & US

Prof. Karen Ferreira-Meyers, University of Eswatini, Eswatini

Savanam Chandra Sekhar, St. Ann's College of Engineering & Technology, Chirala, India

Paige Dou

On behalf of,

The Editorial Board of *Review of European Studies*

Canadian Center of Science and Education